

THE INFLUENCE OF AESTHETICS ON YOUNG PEOPLE'S TRUST OF INFORMATION

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ABSTRACT

We live in a time and place that has been termed “the new age of aesthetics,” in which “design is everywhere, and everywhere is now designed” (Postrel 2003). “Everywhere” could refer to our physical environments as well as to our cultural and informational environments; we find information framed by or contained in various “objects,” which may be print, digital, or multimedia; small- or large-scale; discrete “containers” or immersive environments. I am interested in the ways in which the design of information materials works to communicate with young readers, and how young people interpret the visual and other aesthetics of those materials, as well as how they interpret the text. I am researching the ways in which young people assign credibility to information materials as potentially distinct from the ways in which adults working in the design professions would assign credibility to those same materials. This paper focuses on a research project in progress, regarding information design. The research project takes up to five information materials on the subject of the environment, aimed towards young readers. I will ask up to five designers and up to eight pairs of young people (aged 11-17) to review the information material. I will then compare where their interpretations converge and where they diverge.

KEYWORDS: *information design, adolescents, information literacy, aesthetics, qualitative methods*

INTRODUCTION

This research will examine some affordances and interpretations of information design for young people, based on interview sessions with pairs of young people and individual designers. Taking a selection of five differently designed information materials on the subject of the environment, I examine how two distinct groups interpret those materials: adult designers and young people between the ages of 11-17. I will document participants' discussions about the aesthetic properties of specific information materials. My analysis of their discussions will look to identify how design elements influence (or do not influence) participants' attention to the materials, and to examine some of the ways in which young people talk about design aesthetics. I am particularly interested in how the discussions and terminology used by young research participants regarding the aesthetics of information design may converge or contrast with discussions and terminology provided by the discussions and terminology provided by designers. I am in the early stages of this research, which will be completed by August 2014.

LITERATURE REVIEW

The term “information” is often used in a deceptively neutral way, suggesting that information exists free of influence or affect. Prasad (2005) notes that the writing, design, and reception of an informational text possess an inherent complexity, regardless of what appears to be on the surface, simple. Lanham (2006), a composition scholar, went further when he noted, “clean information is not the destiny of humankind. Clean information is unnatural and unuseful. Information always comes charged with emotion of some kind, full of purpose. That is why we have acquired it.” Here, Lanham suggests that charged information holds an attraction for a reader by virtue of its author position or bias, its attempt to persuade a reader, or its reach. Affect is an integral part of the reason why a reader may seek out information, and may be the reason that information grabs a reader's attention.

Mackey (2007) noted,

Attention is shaped by experience and fuelled by affect; it manifests itself in different parts of the body, in the limbic system of the brain, and in the conscious processes of thought. Attracting, sustaining and directing attention is a major thrust of any

text, whether designed for aesthetic, informational or commercial purposes, or any amalgam of the three.

Any presentation of information comes with a set of cues that suggest whether or not it can be trusted, according to the end reader / viewer. Sundar (2010) notes that these cues are also called heuristics, and can be defined as the signals that a user recognizes, which allow her to make a judgment without cognitively considering other characteristics of the information source. The motivation to pursue cognitive evaluation of an information source—referred to as “systemic processing” by Chaiken (1980)—is influenced by different factors. People have two different modes of processing: the heuristic and the systematic. The heuristic method of processing relies on cues for judgments that are stored in the memory of a viewer or user. It is informally known as the “top down” method of processing. The systematic method of processing relies upon cognitive judgments, and the active evaluation of the information or object at hand, in order to come to a judgment (Chaiken 1980). This is informally known as the “bottom up” method of processing. Clearly, an individual will build up a suite of heuristics over her or his lifetime, based upon other information objects she or he has encountered and judged. An individual will build stereotypes based upon her or his experiences. The more she or he has encountered particular stereotypes, the stronger the resulting heuristic cue for that person.

Reading research is relevant and important here, and serves as a reminder of the complexity involved in communication and learning. Reading theories contribute important concepts to my proposed research, particularly Rosenblatt's (1982) theories of reading stance: efferent reading and aesthetic reading. She suggested that one of these two stances predominate when a reader approaches a particular text at a particular moment in time. In the process of efferent reading, a reader “will narrow his attention to building up the meanings, the ideas, the directions to be retained; attention focuses on accumulating what is to be carried away at the end of the reading.” In contrast, aesthetic reading allows “a much broader range of elements will be allowed to rise into consciousness, not simply the abstract concepts that the words point to, but also what those objects or referents stir up of personal feelings, ideas, and attitudes.” It is extremely important to note that a single text may be read from either of these two stances; Rosenblatt (1991) firmly dismisses any suggestion that the text itself determines a reader's response: “We can read aesthetically something written mainly to inform or read efferently something written mainly to communicate experience. Our present purpose and past experiences, as well as the text, are factors in our choice of stance.”

Within each of these modes exists an opportunity for heuristic cues which either could signal the way in which the mode is meant to be interpreted (e.g., the use of the colour yellow to prompt joy or cheerfulness from a reader / viewer), or could signal that the mode is being employed (e.g., the blue text and underlining of a hyperlink, which suggests interactivity or hypertextuality). To this end, modal heuristics may

relate to a reader's / viewer's assigning of credibility to an information material.

However, as Sundar (2010) warned, “a chasm exists between our expectations about and the effects of digital media, and between our perceived needs and actual use of their offerings.” He used the example of digital media designed for young people, in which he has observed that much attention has been placed on the affordances meant to “dazzle” young users, but which do not result in long-term interest, learning, or use. This example suggests that it is important to avoid the mistakes of technological determinism when considering the design of media for young people (as well as for adults): the development of a particular affordance in the design of information material must work effectively, and on par with the development of the information material's contents. Simply addressing user attention is not going to guarantee interest or use. Heuristics do not necessarily adhere to a standard of credibility or design, and are not “proof” of the quality of the content to which they are attached.

It does seem that heuristics have notable and immediate impacts on media readers / viewers / users. Sundar (2010) quoted Metzger in stating that many people rely most heavily on the elements of design or presentation as heuristics for credibility assessment. And yet, it is extremely complex to understand how design works with readers and users. Lavie and Tractinsky (2004) assert, “The very broad scope of design possibilities, the creative nature of design work, and the almost unbounded relationships between design elements make it extremely difficult to isolate specific design aspects which may be considered aesthetic or which may influence aesthetic perceptions one way or another.” Adjacent to the complications of the interactions of design elements is the Persuasion Knowledge Model (), which outlines that much of the user experience literature presumes end users as not thoughtful readers of products: “they are seen to read the product, but not to recognize that the product has been written.”

RESEARCH METHODS

For the research, I am taking up to five information materials on the subject of the environment, aimed at young readers (between the ages of 11-17). The materials' approach to the subject varies, as some of my selections are scientific, and others focus on consumer or lifestyle choices that impact the environment. I am choosing specific materials for both their individual characteristics, and for the way in which they create a small “collection” of materials. When choosing an individual resource, I consider whether the material is print or digital, colour or black and white, large-format or small-format (for the print materials), and illustrated or primarily textual. I will also consider the interactive affordances each material offered to a reader / user (e.g., an online game as opposed to an online video). Collectively, I will review my collection of materials to determine the extent to which they contrast one

another. I want to ensure that each material sample is reasonably distinct from the others I have chosen. See attached JPEG files for examples of information materials.

Prior to our meeting, I will have asked each of the young people participating in my research to come to the pre-arranged session prepared to show myself and the other participant an “item” that they particularly like: a book, a game, a website, an app. I will ask each person to talk about the item that she or he has brought, to briefly discuss why this item appeals to her or him. I will ask each young person to respond to the others’ selections. This action serves to shift the methods towards a research process that has some focus on the young people, as opposed to focusing strictly on the researcher’s own questions. Barker and Weller (2003), in their work on “children centred research methods,” note that there is benefit to engaging young people, through allowing them at least some space to talk about the things in which they are interested, not just those in which the researcher is interested.

I will then proceed to show the young people the information materials that I have gathered. I will ask the participants to follow a “Think Together” method while they look at the items in front of them. Branch (2006) defined “Think Togethers” as “small-group concurrent verbal reports.” Branch noted, “Researchers can combine Think Alouds, Think Afters, and Think Togethers with additional data-collection methods such as observations, audiotape recordings, and/or video recordings to enhance the overall picture of adolescents’ experiences during instructional activities.”

I will sit with the designers in a ninety-minute session, and will ask them to review the information materials previously described in this proposal. I will ask them to look at the materials and talk about the heuristics they notice, and to discuss their interpretations of the design choices made with those materials. After the review, I will conduct semi-structured interviews to ask several questions about designers’ decision-making processes when they design information materials for young people. I am not specifically seeking out designers of environmental materials for young people, nor am I seeking out the designers of the specific materials, which I am showing to the young people. This is because the materials I am showing to the young people, while chosen with specific criteria in mind, are not singularly important as aesthetic artifacts. However, I may prompt designers for any examples of projects, which may illustrate their narratives about how they consider and realize the design of materials for young people.

I believe that my research will help me investigate how aesthetics connect to particular factors of looking at, seeing, and reading information materials; for example, how they attract and hold some people’s attention, or prompt particular kinds of affective and/or behavioural responses (such as suggesting readability). Through my reading interpretations of sessions with young people and interviews with designers, I look to understand the convergent and divergent understandings of elements found in specific examples of graphic design between these perspectives.

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